

Synthesis of Girinimbine^a

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Girinimbine, C₁₈H₁₇NO, m.p. 176°, the first pyranocarbazole from a plant source was isolated by Chakraborty *et al.*¹ from the stem bark of *Murraya koenigii* Spreng and was considered to have either of the structures I or II². But in considerations, of the physical data the structure (II) was considered more probable by Chakraborty and Chowdhury³. The unequivocal proof of the structure of girinimbine as (II) has been provided by Chakraborty *et al.*⁴ as also by Joshi and Kamat⁵ from degradative and synthetic evidences: Dutta and Quasim⁶, in consideration of spectral data advanced the structure (II) for girinimbine.

In the present communication, we report the synthesis of girinimbine which confirms its structure⁴⁻⁶. To the phenolic substrate, 2-hydroxy-3-methyl carbazole (III)⁷, C₁₃H₁₁NO, m.p. 245°, the C₅-residue was introduced using the method and procedure similar to that used in the synthesis of the 6-methyl analogue of dihydrogirinimbine by Chakraborty *et al.*⁸

β : β -Dimethyl acrylyl chloride in pyridine at 5° was condensed with the compound (III), when the acyl derivative (IV), C₁₈H₁₇NO₂,^b m.p. 200° was obtained. The above compound on Fries rearrangement in presence of AlCl₃ in dry nitrobenzene for 5 hrs and on subsequent cyclisation, with conc. HCl afforded the indolo-chromanone (V), C₁₈H₁₇NO₂, m.p. 160-65°, $\lambda_{max}^{ethanol}$ 228, 282, 287, $m\mu$ with log ϵ 4.65, 4.09, 4.22. On reduction with sodium borohydride, the compound (V) afforded the alcohol (VI), C₁₈H₁₉NO₂, m.p. 160°, $\lambda_{max}^{ethanol}$ 237, 252, 303 $m\mu$ with log ϵ 4.7, 4.3 and 4.24, the tosyl derivative (VII) of which on dehydrotosylation in presence of collidine furnished girinimbine, C₁₈H₁₇NO, m.p. 172°,

(a) Part XVII in the Series Chemical Taxonomy. Part XXVI; D. P. Chakraborty, K. C. Das, B. K. Chowdhury (in press) and from D.Phil. thesis of A. Islam, Jan., 1970.

(b) Satisfactory analytical data were obtained for new compounds with mol. formula.

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(b) D. Chatterjee, D. Phil. thesis., Cal. Univ., 1968.

identical with the natural product (m.m.p., 176°; uv., ir). This confirms the structure of girinimbine as (II) and settles the structure of murrayacine⁹⁷⁴ (VIII) which was shown to be the 3-formyl analogue of girinimbine.

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